

Zooplankton Diversity of Dongergaon Water Tank Dongergaon Dist Latur (M.S)

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Abstract:

The present paper deals with the zooplankton diversity of Dongergaon water tank Dongergaon. The qualitative and quantitative analysis of zooplankton was carried out from Feb 2022 to Jan 2023. Different species of zooplankton were identified. The zooplanktons are the indicators of ecological status of any aquatic body. Zooplankton is one of the important stage in aquatic food chain where they are directly fed by small fishes.

Key words:- Zooplanktons, Dongergaon water tank.

Introduction:

The fresh water communities like fishes, macrophytes, microphytes, phytoplankton and zooplankton are sensitive to physical chemical changes in any aquatic water body. It also demonstrates ecological status of that water body. The planktons form an important stage in aquatic food chain. The productivity of the water body lot more depend upon these primary stages in the food chain, Michale (1973). There has been considerable interest in the relevance of limnological information to the productivity, development and management of aquatic environments.

Materials and Methods:

For the estimation of zooplanktons the water samples were collected from four different stations of Dongergaon water tank. These are station A, Station B, Station C and Station D. The samples were collected in different seasons, monthly and were preserved in 4% formalin for quantitative and qualitative analysis of zooplanktons. Plankton samples were collected with standard plankton net made of silk bolting cloth no.25. The amount of water filtered was 200 lit and the samples were concentrated to 50 ml volume. Each replicate of phytoplankton and zooplankton samples was identified under research microscope using suitable keys, standard texts and monographs given by Pennak (1978), Tonapi (1980), APHA (1985), fresh water biology by Vard and Wipple, Zooplankton by Battis, The book of IABA, Hyderabad for water analysis methods.

Result and Discussion:

Monthly water samples from tank water were collected to study quantitative and qualitative data of various zooplanktons. Rotifers were represented by 8 species, Cladocerans by 6 species and Copepods by 3 species. The list of zooplankton was given in table no 1.

Among the total zoo planktonic organisms rotifer come first in order of abundance. Rotifers were represented by 8 species. Keratella was dominated in the tank. The highest density of rotifers was observed in the month of April and May. Throughout the summer months rotifer population was maximum however, during winter season, the rotifer population was comparatively less. The Rotifers Keratella cochlearis, K. procura, Macrochaetus collinsi and Philodina citrine were dominant in summer month. The genus Keratella was represented by 2 species.

Cladocerans were represented by 6 species. Among cladocerans Monia and Alona dominated the tank. During summer and early monsoon there was a dominance of Moina brachiata and Alona quadrangularis.

Copepods were represented by 3 species. The copepods Cyclops, mesocyclops in copepoid stage were dominated. The density of copepods population was more during summer and least during late rainy and early winter season. A minor peak of the population of copepods was seen during December and January while major peak being in April and May.

Table 1. Zooplankton Diversity In Dongergaon Water Tank Dongergaon, During Feb 2022-Jan 2023

Sr. No.	Group	Species
1	Rotifera	<i>Brachionus forficula</i>
		<i>Keratella cochlearis</i>
		<i>Keratella procura</i>
		<i>Notholca striata</i>
		<i>Lecane bulla</i>
		<i>Macrochaetus collinsi</i>
		<i>Philodina citrine</i>
		<i>Filinia opoliensis</i>
2	Cladocera	<i>Daphnia carinata</i>
		<i>Ceriodaphnia cornuta</i>

		<i>Moina brachiate</i>
		<i>Moina micrura</i>
		<i>Bosmina longirostris</i>
		<i>Alona quadrangularis</i>
3	Copepoda	<i>Mesocyclop sps</i>
		<i>Cyclop sps</i>
		<i>Nauplius Larvae</i>

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